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Case Study

Paracetamol-Induced Hepatotoxicity In A Malnourished Patient– A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Acetaminophen, an analgesic and antipyretic with a favorable safety profile is used globally. However, excessive doses can lead to severe hepatotoxicity and acute liver failure. We present a case report that describes the unfortunate demise of a 48-year-old male patient with carcinoma colon who developed severe hepatotoxicity attributed to paracetamol administration following right radical hemicolectomy. Despite the patient receiving paracetamol at a dosage below the recommended limit under medical supervision, he experienced a rapid deterioration in liver function, leading to a cascade of life-threatening complications. The intricate interplay between medication administration and patient-specific factors emphasizes the ongoing imperative for the medical community to evolve and optimize treatment strategies for improved patient outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Paracetamol (Acetaminophen), widely used as an antipyretic, analgesic and over the counter medication which has a good safety profile but higher doses may lead to severe hepatotoxicity. (1,2) In 1893, it was first time used clinically by Von Mering. Paracetamol was not commercially available in the United States until 1950, and in Australia until 1956. (3) The USFDA (United states food and drug administration) stated that it is safe to consume paracetamol up to maximum dose of 4 grams within 24 hours. The European

Medicine Insert Dosing Guidelines recommends a maximum of 3g of paracetamol for older adults who weigh less than 50 kg or more than 50 kg with additional risk factors for hepatotoxicity. (4) Paracetamol overdose is one of the commonest causes for acute hepatic failure. (5) Studies have shown that the adult population suffering from acute hepatic failure (40%) was due to paracetamol overdose which was taken by unintentionally or for the purpose of suicide. (6) About 10% of any queries to the UK National Poisons Information Service and 73,000 (more than 1,13,000 including preparations containing

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paracetamol) reports to the Toxic Exposure Surveillance Scheme of the American Association of Poison Control Centres in 1996 were prompted by worries about paracetamol overdose. (7) Recently, paracetamol overdose has been more troublesome because of its over-the-counter use and in combination with other medications. (8) Hepatotoxicity caused by an overdose of paracetamol is the primary cause of acute liver failure (ALF) in the United States and several areas of Europe, accounting for more than half of ALF cases in these locations. (9) If paracetamol overdose is noticed early the mortality rate is low, once the acute hepatic failure has developed the mortality rate is approximately 28% and one of the third patient required liver transplantation.(10)

CASE REPORT

A middle-aged man presented with carcinoma colon developed acute hepatic failure on receiving paracetamol 3g/day under medical supervision during hospitalization. On admission he appeared severely malnourished as per the weight for height standards, the patient weighed about 32kg and 145cm in height. He was admitted for a planned surgery of right radical hemicolectomy on 21 December 2023. The pre-operative records showed that the patient was stable and the blood routine i.e., LFT, RFT, ABG, ECG were all within the normal limits (as shown in the Table no.1). The patient underwent surgery of right radical hemicolectomy under epidural anaesthesia with vecuronium, suxamethonium and propofol along with prophylactic antibiotics ceftriaxone and metronidazole. Morphine was given as postoperative analgesia for pain management. Paracetamol 1g TID was initiated postoperatively on 22 Dec 2023, advised nothing per oral for 20 h. Seven days after commencement of paracetamol, patient complained of severe pain in the right upper quadrant, breathlessness, dizziness and per rectal bleed. Following assessment, haematological investigations revealed

abnormalities, as the table illustrates. Serum alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) levels were significantly elevated, with 750 IU L⁻¹ and 812 IU L⁻¹, respectively, in liver function tests. Paracetamol use was discontinued. The characteristic pattern of elevated liver enzymes and lack of a history of other co-morbidities aggravating the same led to the diagnosis of paracetamol-related acute liver failure. Viral and serological testing was ruled out, acute infection with enteroviruses, adenovirus, cytomegalovirus, Epstein-Barr virus, herpes simplex virus, varicella-zoster virus, and hepatitis viruses A, B, C, and E were all negative. Considering the severity and pattern of the liver enzyme abnormalities, hepatotoxicity from other drugs appeared unlikely. The patient was still hemodynamically unstable the next day, but he was alert, somnolent, and compliant with commands. On RS examination, bilateral crepts were observed. USG abdominal examination revealed mild ascites, pleural effusion, and hepatomegaly. The patient was started on an O₂ mask, Vitamin-K, N-acetylcysteine 150mg/kg loading dose followed by 1gm for 24 hours, and glucose via intravenous infusion. Following a gastroenterologist's recommendation, human albumin 20%, glutathione 600mg, and L-ornithine 30mg were administered intravenously. The patient was unresponsive to commands, had bradycardia (40 beats per minute), and was unable to be awakened on December 29, 2023, at 6 a.m. The patient was immediately started on a nor adrenaline infusion; he had a poor prognosis, and his condition deteriorated further as he went into an arrest. Both the pulse and blood pressure could not be measured. The ACLS protocol was followed, and multiple IV atropine and adrenaline doses were administered along with the rapid start of CPR. Furthermore, blood pressure could not be recorded, and pupils were dilated and fixed. An

ECG revealed a flat line. Despite all emergency treatments, the patient did not survive and was declared dead at 7:30 a.m.

Table no.1

Hematological investigations					
Sr. No	Test parameter	Pre-operative Result	7- days after commencement of paracetamol Result	Unit	Normal range
1	Hemoglobin	15.1	11.3	gms/dl	13.-17.0
2	Platelet count	3.80	3.17	Lakhs/cmm	1.5-4.1
3	WBC Count	9800	7870	Cells/cumm	4000-10000
4	Blood Urea	22		mg/dl	16.6-45.5
5	Creatinine (Serum)	0.7	1.29	mg/dl	0.7-1.4
6	Sodium	136	129	mmol/L	136-145
7	Potassium	3.8	3.2	mmol/L	3.5-5.1
8	Chloride	99	98	mmol/L	98-107
9	Bilirubin Total	0.6	2.46	mg/dl	0.0-1.0
10	Bilirubin Direct	0.2	2.24	mg/dl	0.0-0.2
11	Bilirubin Indirect	0.4	0.22	mg/dl	0.0-1.0
12	SGOT (AST)	23	812	mg/dl	6-40
13	SGPT	18	750	mg/dl	6-40
14	Alkaline phosphatase	129	165	U/L	50-126
15	Total Protein	6.1	3.0	g/dl	6.0-8.5
16	Albumin	3.6	1.7	g/dl	3.4-5
17	Globulin	2.50	1.3	g/dl	2.5-3.8
18	Gamma Glutamyl Transferase		599	U/L	15-73
19	A/G Ratio	1.44	1.31		1.0-2.1
20	Prothrombin/INR	18.2/1.40	112/7.6	sec	11-14
21	Partial Thromboplastin Time	36.6		sec	25-37

DISCUSSION:

Children are less likely than adults to experience a fatal overdose of paracetamol that results in encephalopathy and toxic liver injury. (7) Drug metabolism and the elimination of toxins and other substances from the human body are carried out by the liver. (11) During the metabolic pathway of paracetamol, 2-10% of it is metabolized to N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone imine (NAPQI), a reactive intermediate that mediates paracetamol's hepatotoxicity. Overdosage or the presence of

other pathological or physiological states cause an increase in the percentage of the dose metabolized by this pathway. (12,13,14) A healthy individual with sufficient GSH stores is capable of detoxifying this harmful metabolite of paracetamol whereas individuals with underlying co-morbidities or disrupted hepatic function with depleted GSH are incapable of detoxifying NAPQI further causing cellular injury by the process of oxidation. (15) Studies suggests that alcohol consumption and starvation may increase the

synthesis of NAPQI due to depleted GSH stores especially when paracetamol is given in multiple doses (16). Malnutrition and starvation reduce liver glycogen storage thus reducing UGT (Uridine diphosphate-glucuronyltransferase) conjugative ability producing larger oxidized NAPQI. (17) Alcohol consumption increases the risk of paracetamol toxicity due to CYP2E1 induction, reduction in hepatic GSH or due to reduced glucuronidation. (18) We report a case of middle-aged male patient with no significant comorbidities presented with carcinoma colon. Paracetamol (3g thrice daily) was initiated post operatively for 7 days further which patient complained of discomfort in the right upper quadrant with dizziness on through examination, elevated serum AST and ALT suggested paracetamol induced hepatotoxicity with relevant contributing risk factors. Here though paracetamol was given as per the recommended dose it was observed that paracetamol induced hepatotoxicity mainly occur as a result of malnutrition, as paracetamol was given for 7 consecutive days patient condition deteriorated despite administration of NAC (N- acetyl cysteine) and other live protectants such as L-Orthenine. The patient's health worsened, eventually resulting to death. Therefore, individualising paracetamol dosing especially in malnutrition, alcoholics and patients with underlying diseases is recommended to minimise such fatal events. (19)

CONCLUSION:

This case highlights the critical importance of maintaining vigilance when administering paracetamol, even when it is prescribed within recommended limits. The occurrence of severe hepatotoxicity with a fatal outcome demonstrates the multifactorial nature of drug-induced liver injury. The patient's malnutrition and the consecutive seven-day administration of paracetamol, despite being less than the recommended dosage, contributed to the

disastrous outcome. The case highlights the importance of individualised dosing strategies, particularly in patients with underlying health conditions, malnutrition, or reduced drug metabolism. To avoid serious side effects linked to paracetamol use, clinicians need to be cautious about potential risk factors, monitor closely, and consider other analgesic options. The subtle interactions between medication administration and patient-specific factors are poignantly brought to light by this report, which suggests the medical community to continuously refine therapeutic approaches to enhance patient safety.

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